

The effect on leaffolder damage of different methods of applying nitrogen was investigated further in a split-plot design with two nitrogen levels (main treatment) and seven methods of application (subtreatments). In some treatments N as urea was applied to the root zone

with an applicator or by hand in paper balls. Fenitrothion (0.05%) was sprayed at 40 DT, and fenthion (0.05%) at 55 DT. Leaffolder infestation was assessed by recording the percentage of damaged leaves at 60 DT when the pest occurrence was highest.

Applying all the N basally tended to increase the leaffolder damage level above that with use of other methods (see table). But at a moderate N level, the application method appeared to have little effect on leaffolder damage. ■

Pest management and control WEEDS

Propagation of perennial paddy weeds in unplanted paddy fields

Jiro Harada, Hokuriku National Agricultural Experiment Station, Joetsu, Niigata 943-01, Japan

Recent agricultural policy on surplus rice in Japan increased the unplanted paddy fields all over the country. Perennial paddy weeds proliferated in such fields and their propagules were spread by plowing and puddling. This seems to be one reason for the recent rapid increase of perennial paddy weeds.

To determine the propagation ability of a single plant in unplanted paddy fields, an experiment used five serious perennial paddy weeds: *Sagittaria pygmaea* Miq. (Sp), *Cyperus serotinus* Rottb. (Cs), *Eleocharis kuroguwai* Ohwi (Ek), *Scirpus planiculmis* Fr. Schm. (Spl), and *Potamogeton distinctus* A. Benn. (Pd). The field was plowed and puddled after a uniform application of 50 kg N/ha, 100 kg P₂O₅/ha, and 100 kg K₂O/ha. One plant of each weed was transplanted in the center of a 9-m² plot separately on 10 June 1981. Hand weeding was carried out to avoid the effect of other weeds. The number of plants, the occupied land area, and the plant den-

Distribution map of perennial paddy weeds propagated from a single plant. Niigata, Japan, 1980.

Propagation from a single plant of perennial paddy weeds in an unplanted paddy field. Niigata, Japan, 1980.

Weed species	Plants ^a (no.)	Occupied land area ^a (m ²)	Density ^a (plants/m ²)	Propagules ^b	
				No.	Fresh wt (g)
<i>Sagittaria pygmaea</i>	313	0.939	333.3	822	41.1
<i>Cyperus serotinus</i>	321	1.551	210.8	794	190.0
<i>Eleocharis kuroguwai</i>	51	0.793	71.9	51	68.2
<i>Scirpus planiculmis</i>	214	3.494	61.2	1,244	1295.9
<i>Potamogeton distinctus</i>	457	2.615	174.8	118	24.7

^aExamined on 5 August 1980. ^bExamined on 12 November 1980.

sity were examined on 5 August and the propagules formed were examined on 12 November.

The results are shown in the figure and the table. Considerable propagules

were formed even in the least propagated weed. The results suggest that a few weeds remaining in the unplanted part of a paddy field is a big source of propagules for the following year. ■

Efficiency of fluchloralin, butachlor, nitrofen, and hand weeding for rice weed control

S. K. Mukhopadhyay and A. Mondal, College of Agriculture (P.S.S.), Visva-Bharati University, India

A field experiment at the Agricultural College Farm (Palli Siksha Sadana),

Sriniketan, Visva-Bharati, West Bengal during 1979 kharif studied the comparative efficiency of some granular herbicides and hand weeding for controlling weeds in the semihumid lateritic tract of the state. There were 12 weed species: 3 were grasses, 3 were sedges, and 6 were broadleaved of which *Echinochloa crus-galli*, *E. colona*, and *Ludwigia perennis*

were predominant in the experimental field. The granular herbicides fluchloralin at 2.0 kg a.i./ha 7 days after transplanting (DT), nitrofen 1.5 kg and 2.0 kg a.i./ha 6 DT, and butachlor at 2.0 kg a.i./ha 6 DT reduced the weed population but showed no injurious effect on the crop (see table). Nitrofen and butachlor gave very promising results in

Effects of granular herbicides and hand weeding on weed wt and rice yield. West Bengal, India.

Treatment ^a	Dry wt of weeds at 60 DT (g/m ²)	Yield of rice grain (t/ha)
Fluchloralin 1.5 kg 1 DBT	19.05	2.9
Fluchloralin 2.0 kg 1 DBT	16.81	3.0
Fluchloralin 1.5 kg 1 DT	13.46	2.8
Fluchloralin 2.0 kg 1 DT	11.34	2.7
Fluchloralin 1.5 kg 7 DT	10.04	3.2
Fluchloralin 2.0 kg 7 DT	6.48	3.7
Butachlor 1.5 kg 6 DT	5.74	3.5
Butachlor 2.0 kg 6 DT	3.92	3.6
Nitrofen 1.5 kg 6 DT	3.93	3.4
Nitrofen 2.0 kg 6 DT	2.23	3.8
Hand weeding, 25 & 50 DT	3.82	3.5
Unweeded control	52.95	2.3
S.Em ±	2.71	.06
C.D. at 5% level	8.40	1.90

^aDBT = days before transplanting, DT = days after transplanting. All herbicide doses are in active ingredient per hectare.

controlling all categories of weeds. Fluchloralin 2.0 kg a.i./ha at 7 DT showed very effective reduction of broadleaved and grass weeds. The dry weight of weeds at 60 DT was very much reduced after the application of nitrofen at 6 DT, butachlor at 6 DT, and fluchloralin at 7 DT compared to the other treatments. Nitrofen granules at 2 kg ai/ha applied 6 DT gave the highest yield of rice grain, closely followed by fluchloralin 2.0 kg a.i./ha at 7 DT, butachlor (G) 2.0 kg a.i./ha at 6 DT, and 2 hand weedings. As high as 37.69% loss in grain yield was observed with no weeding compared with the best treatment (nitrofen 2.0 kg a.i./ha 6 DT). ■

Weed control in deepwater rice in Bangladesh

M. Zahidul Hoque (present address: Multiple Cropping Department, IRRRI), head; Nur-E-Elahi, senior scientific officer; and Mainur Rahman Siddiqui, scientific officer, Division of Rice Cropping Systems, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute (BRRI), Joydebpur, Dacca, Bangladesh

In Bangladesh, deepwater rice is also known as broadcast aman (b. aman) rice because the seeds are sown by broadcasting in March-April with the first monsoon showers. As in any direct-seeded rice, weeds are a serious problem in the deepwater rice crop. Farmers in

Bangladesh with about 2 million ha (about 20% of the total rice area) of deepwater rice use raking, laddering, and hand weeding to control weeds in the b. aman rice fields. Sometimes the farmers allow the weeds to grow to a certain height and then use them as fodder, which commands a good market price in the deepwater rice belt.

In 1980, farmers' weed control practices at the BRRI deepwater rice-based cropping systems research site at Daudkandi were monitored. The results showed that, on the average, 1, 2, and 3 hand weedings were done by 22.5, 67.5, and 10% of the farmers (see table). The average time for hand weedings was 33 days after seeding (DS) for the first

hand weeding, 51 DS for the second, and 75 DS for the third.

Triple hand weedings were used on two popular varieties Kartiksail and Sada Pankaish, the third weeding applied between 73 and 89 DS. Double hand weeding as practised in Ejuli Khama and Dulai Aman was completed between 44 and 54 DS. A small number of farmers grew varieties Bhatial Bajal and An Raj and applied only one hand weeding either at a very delayed (58 DS) or a very early (11 DS) date, but within 29 April and 7 May, the time of first flush of weeds after the initial monsoon rains (see table). More detailed weed studies at the site are planned. ■

Frequency and timing of farmers' hand weeding in the 1980 deepwater rice crop at the BRRI cropping systems research site, Daudkandi, Comilla district, Bangladesh.^a

Deepwater rice variety	Samples (no.)	Av seeding date	Farmers (%) applying			Time of HW (DS)			Maturity (DS)
			1 HW	2 HW	3 HW	1st HW	2d HW	3d HW	
Kartiksail	18	9 Apr	11	72	17	27	49	13	215
Sada Pankaish	8	11 Apr	24	63	13	30	55	89	221
Ejuli Khama	8	15 Apr	12	88	—	21	44	—	206
Dulai Aman	3	2 Apr	33	67	—	35	54	—	230
Bhatial Bajal	2	30 Mar	100	—	—	58	—	—	230
Ari Raj	1	26 Apr	100	—	—	11	—	—	201
Av		10 Apr	22.5	67.5	10	33	51	75	216

^aHW = hand weeding, DS = days after seeding.

The International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN) invites all scientists to contribute concise summaries of significant rice research for publication. Contributions should be limited to one or two pages and no more than two short tables, figures, or photographs. Contributions are subject to editing and abridgement to meet space limitations. Authors will be identified by name, title, and research organization.